

A Survey on Multimedia over 5G Networks for D2D Communication Based Wi-Fi Direct Technology

Mohamed E. A. Ebrahim¹, Ammar Mohammed²

Abstract

Smart-Device to Smart-Device (D2D) communications over Wi-Fi Direct (WFD) technologies in 5G networks still face many dilemmas especially if some services available to the users such as social sharing of video streaming, audio, and caching solutions, with a massive number of mobile users, considering rate-distortion (RD) characteristics for QoS with finding the best way to calculate distance between multi-hop candidate devices and whether the device is static or moving about characteristics of flow traffic speed such as High-Speed railways and subway with the mobility feature of communications according to the future demands in 5G. In this article, we present a survey of current methodologies and techniques related to neighboring discovery in the network area, interference management, low energy consumption communication, and its impact on multimedia delivery.

Keywords: D2D Communication, Proximity Services (ProSe), Wi-Fi Direct (WFD), Rate-Distortion (RD), 5G, Internet of Smart-Things (IoST), Smart-Device (SD).

1. Introduction

Electronic Smart-Devices (SD) are developing rapidly and significantly, and thus the volume of user requests will increase consequently data traffic will grow in the future, monthly data traffic global will be 77 XB by 2022, and annual traffic will reach about zettabyte [1][14]. Users' concerns emphasize the importance of supporting various multimedia devices with minimizing latency time [2], such as text, audio, graphics, images, animation, video, interactive content, etc. [3][8]. Therefore, based on the goals and requirements of 5G, it is smarter, more efficient, and much faster [9]. Now with D2D communications technology, we have faced many challenges for multimedia delivery. There are many topics researchers have tried to provide ideas and logical solutions to reach the requirements of the fifth generation of communications to support D2D communications especially Wi-Fi Direct because of a potential candidate for outband D2D communication [4][5].

¹Computer Sciences Department, Faculty of Graduate Studies for Statistical Research, Cairo University.

²Computer Sciences Department, Faculty of Graduate Studies for Statistical Research, Cairo University.

D2D is not user equipment only but expanded to include for example, personal computers, smart mobile phones, laptops, netbooks, multimedia players, MP3 players, and Smart-Machine to Smart-Machine M2M, and also a Smart-Vehicle to Smart-Vehicle V2V, with 5G IoT [6][7]. In addition, Smart-Machine to Everything M2X and Smart-Vehicle to Everything V2X. The main contributions of this paper are to provide a Summary of Cases related to Smart-Device to Smart-Device (D2D) communications in 5G and a discussion of techniques in previous works regarding Network Topology with the presentation of Analytical Tools used. This paper is organized as follows. Section 2 provides an overview of D2D. In Section 3, types of wireless communication. Licensed cellular spectrum and unlicensed cellular spectrum for D2D communication were briefly discussed in Section 4. In Section 5, categorize the challenges of D2D communication and view some of the previous work and how you faced those challenges, In Section 6, present research issues related to the future of D2D then display the advantages and disadvantages of ProSe technology in Section 7.

2. Smart-Device to Smart-device

Smart-Device to Smart-Device Communications, also known as proximity services (ProSe) Communication, is part of the 3GPP (LTP) architecture [10] this means that two Smart-Devices (SDs) communicate directly without a base station BS and the underlying network, and include Long-Term Evolution LTE-Assisted D2D communications and direct communications as V2V. The ProSe communication is also expected to become an essential part of Internet objects and communications from Smart-Vehicle to Smart-Vehicle or Smart-Vehicle to Everything (V2X), where ProSe will be used to pass any information from the vehicle to any entity that may affect the vehicle and vice versa [11]. D2D cellular-assisted communication is a technique that allows terminals to multiplex the resources of direct-cell communication under cellular system control. D2D communications can solve the lack of spectrum resources in the wireless communications system to some extent while improving the spectrum efficiency of the cellular communications system CCS and decreasing the transmission capacity of the terminal [35]. In addition, reducing the consumption of the mobile terminal battery power [36], reduces the load of the cellular network, improves network infrastructure, increases the transmission rate [37], and supports P2P data services [5][10].

3. Radio communication types for the Smart-Device to Smart-Device

Many technologies support a direct connection between Smart-Device to Smart-Device D2D. We will review which are essentially for D2D communication and particular Wi-Fi Direct, Bluetooth, Zigbee, NFC, and RFID [20] and briefly review the key features of available D2D technologies [7].

3.1 Wi-Fi Direct

Recently some advances have been made to new Wi-Fi Direct WFD is the protocol that provides new features that enable Wi-Fi to make discovery and connectivity faster and more efficient [5][7][12]. In addition, the Smart-Device (SD) also allows you to host multiple AP access points to others during the connection, which means better flexibility for Smart-Devices (SDs) in setting up D2D communication. Thus, Wi-Fi Direct can create or accept as many connections of independent as possible, it is very convenient as a MAC layer for Smart-Device to Smart-Device Communication [5][13].

3.2 Bluetooth

Bluetooth, along with the Wi-Fi network, is the most popular D2D technology on the unlicensed band. Bluetooth provides Wireless connectivity in private domain networks. to enable short-range communication, one master of communication that serves up to seven users to form Bluetooth architecture. Bluetooth Low Energy was recently standardized for the Internet of SmartThings IoST and opens doors to new application scenarios by exploiting smartphone connectivity [7][5].

3.3 Zigbee

Zigbee is a set of protocols dedicated to wireless sensor networks with limited resources. It is the MAC layers that determine the balanced trade-off between the data rate, the communication range, and energy efficiency. [7] Several enhancements have been proposed, including IEEE 802.15.4E standard and IEEE 802.15.4G. The former MAC layer has been redesigned to support industry-specific applications specifically, by introducing time sync and switch channels. The latter handles ultra-wide sensor networks, such as smart utility networks [5].

3.4 NFC

Near-field communication NFC plays a prominent role in its widespread adoption, being locally incorporated into modern smart mobiles. In addition to interacting with tags, it expects a Peer-to-Peer P2P mode through which Smart-Devices (SDs) can exchange any type of data directly. This technology promotes the widespread Internet of SmartThings IoST system [7][68].

3.5 RFID

Radio-frequency identification RFID refers to a set of radio techniques whose main purpose is to provide quick recognition of objects through interaction between transceivers, also known as tags and readers. Different classifications of RFID systems can be provided according to the operating frequency, radio interface, communication group, tag independence, and various standards that have been ratified. For short-range communications [69][70]. Table 1 shows a comparison of types of D2D communication technologies.

TABLE 1: Comparison of types D2D technologies [71][72]

Parameter	Wi-Fi Direct (WFD)	Bluetooth	Zigbee	NFC	RFID (UHF)
Range	up to 200 m	10–100 m	10–100 m	4–10 cm	up to 100 m
Data Rate	up to 250 Mbps	0.8–2.1 Mbps	0.02–0.2 Mbps	0.02–0.4 Mbps	up to 640 kbps
Power consumption	High	High	Medium	Low	High
Spectrum	2.4 GHz	2.4 GHz	2.4 GHz	13.56 MHz	433 MHz
Security	High	Low	Low	High	High
Network topology	One to one one-to-many	Piconets, scatternets	Star, tree, mesh	One to one	One to one
Devices per network	up to 8 devices	8	2–65, 536	2	1

4. 3GPP LTE Overview for Smart-Device to Smart-Device Communications

At first, D2D was linked to LTE-A, which is part of 3GPP Rel.12, [4][15][16] and expected to be D2D cellular communication technology is fully unified for proximity services ProSe in the next 3GPP Rel.13 and 14 and highlighted evolution of D2D concept of Smart-Vehicle to Everything V2X communication [7][17]. Under the IEEE 802.11 protocol, the D2D concept was introduced on WFD. This allows WFD to play an active role from an access point, which is one of the main advantages of using Smart-Device to Smart-Device networks [4]. Recently, Wi-Fi Direct technology has been available on mobile phones, which will help deploy WFD-based Smart-Device to Smart-Device networks [5]. ProSe communication is an appropriate technique for multimedia-sharing services that rely on proximity. Therefore, it is suitable for 5G networks in the future. Instead of cellular networks, direct connections between Smart-Devices (SDs) make use of nearness. ProSe communications are categorized into Inband connections and Outband D2D [4][17].

4.1 Smart-Device to Smart-Device communication in licensed cellular spectrum

The licensed Cellular spectrum (Inband D2D Communications) provides spectral efficiency because of the spectrum sharing licensed between D2D Communications and cellular network users [4] [18]. The quality management mechanism is controlled by LTE eNBs evolved Node Base stations BSs to manage radio resource and mobility in the cell to optimize all the user equipments UE's communication in a radio network structure, which helps to address problems such as interference [19]. Inband communications can be divided into underlay and overlay [20]. In underlay D2D mobile phone users and D2D communications share the same spectrum resources, while in D2D communications overlay, dedicated spectrum resources are allocated to D2D users. D2D-based communications represent related challenges in *interference management* and *resource allocation* between Smart-Device to Smart-Device D2D users and Long-Term Evolution LTE users. Overlay D2D communication overcomes on interference management and resource distribution problems but does not guarantee the efficient use of resources [7][20][21].

4.2 Smart-Device to Smart-Device communication in unlicensed cellular spectrum

The unlicensed Cellular spectrum (Outband D2D Communications) e.g. Industrial, scientific, and medical domains (ISMs) are international radio bands for radio use. Wi-Fi Direct WFD is the perfect choice for Outband D2D to now. It is necessary to have an additional interface that applies Wi-Fi Direct, Zigbee, or Bluetooth to use an unlicensed spectrum [4][20]. The main goal of exploiting Outband D2D communication is the ability to remove interference between D2D communications. D2D Outband communications face many challenges in coordination between different bands [18][20].

5. Classification challenges of Smart-Device to Smart-Device Communications

D2D communications challenges in the cellular network can be categorized into both (*interference management* and *resource allocation*) based on Inband D2D and (*an extra interface* and *cluster communication*) based on Outband D2D. After we reviewed D2D communications types and the challenges, in this section, we will mention the work of the researchers and their contribution to providing ideas and solutions to the challenges of Smart-Device to Smart-Device Communication with a focus on the social sharing of multimedia streaming. Several authors like [22][23][25][26][27][30][34] proposed the scheduling algorithms and scheduling scheme for sharing multimedia using Smart-Device to Smart-Device D2D, the scenarios take considering interference by ranking the neighboring UEs. In [22][23][24][25][26][31] authors provided optimal rates for caching files at random. Cached and segmented Video download techniques in [26][33]. In [27][30][31][32][41][47] developed framework probability to measure the video playback quality and intelligent emotion in 5G. In the proposed system in [28][29][49][50][55][58] the video is split into data packets and users and uses one cluster for the same packet users. In [30][31][58] proposed a D2D local caching to provide better video download services in a socially conscious environment. Presented in [32] successful connection without human interaction based on Smart-Device to Smart-Device D2D Communication. In [33][49][54][60][62][67] the authors focus on video sharing and energy in 5G networks for D2D. In [6][34] the authors proposed a resource-sharing scheme for multiple D2D groups and cellular users. For a better comparison of the use of caching techniques [37][38][39][60]. Paper [41][47][50][51][56][57][60][62] presents a framework-based cross-layer for resource allocation of the network for the transmission of (High-Efficiency Video Coding) encoded video streams in 5G. In [40] proposed (Ultra-High-Definition) 5G-UHD framework achieves adaptive for video streaming. The authors in [42] analyzed network-assisted D2D clustering in 5G cellular networks using Wi-Fi Direct and LTE-A. In [43][55] proposed a cluster-based D2D communication in vehicular networks. The proposed methodology uses distance as a parameter for radio resource allocation in Smart-Device to Smart-Device, in [26][37][38][44][45]. Some authors use Classification algorithms based on features extracted from previous data like IoT

module classification in [52][63] and use Scheduling algorithms, Stochastic algorithms, and Machine Learning algorithms. Finally, the summary of the literature is proposed in Table 2 and discussed in Table 3.

TABLE 2: Summary of the literature proposed

Ref. no	Proposal	Analytical tools	Platform	Use-case	Technique	Network Topology
[22][56]	- Proposed a method to use Wi-Fi links efficiently. - watermarking scheme proposed for enhanced high-efficiency video coding standard.	-Prefetching algorithm -Extraction algorithm	LTE 5G 4G	-Video streaming -Video caching - video coding	- Resource allocation	-Wi-Fi Direct -Wi-Fi Hotspot -D2D
[22][23] [25][26] [27][30] [34][46] [58][47] [40][62] [66][57]	-Proposed the scheduling algorithms for sharing multimedia content effectively over Smart-Device to Smart-Device communication. - Proposed scheduling algorithms for quality video streaming that can be used for Smart-Device to Smart-Device video delivery applications. -Proposed scheduling algorithm for seamless transmission of data packets over the network.	-Distribution Scheduling algorithms -Stochastic algorithm -PSNR - Fuzzy Round Robin Scheduling algorithm -keyed-hash message Authentication code algorithm - load balancing algorithm - streaming algorithm	5G LTE	-Video streaming sharing - data packets - multimedia transmission	- Resource allocation -Interference Management -M2M cluster	-Cellular -D2D -M2M -Wi-Fi - IEEE - Cloud -Ad-hoc -P2P
[24][48] [33][50] [61][30]	-Proposed scheme as Random Popularity-based caching with colored indexing Coding. - Proposed edge computing framework for video processing groups based on Smart-Device to Smart-Device cluster.	-A greedy algorithm -A greedy coloring -Beyond scaling laws - brute force algorithm -formation algorithm -matching algorithm -heuristic algorithm	5G LTE	- Caching files -Video streaming	-D2D cluster -Interference Management	-D2D -Wi-Fi Direct -Cellular - Cloud
[26][37] [38][39] [45]	-Proposed improving the throughput of video transport in LTE networks. -Caching techniques.	-Distance algorithms -shortest distance algorithm	5G LTE- A	-Cached and segmented video download -Video streaming -voice call	-Interference Management -Resource allocation - D2D cluster	-Cellular -Bluetooth -Wi-Fi Direct
[27][73] [74]	- Proposed development framework based on probability to measure the video quality. - Proposed predicting the QoE of video streaming service based on the non-linear regression function.	-Probability Density Function -PSNR -Scalable video coding -Block Error Rate - nonlinear regression - particle swarm optimization algorithm	LTE	-video playback quality - Video streaming	-Interference Management -Resource allocation	-Cellular -D2D
[28][29] [59]	- Proposed providing functional features not only for the media but, also for information usage of a user Smart-Device (SD). - Proposed split video into multiple data packets and users. -Proposed an image enhancement algorithm based on the improved non-saturating game.	-signal-to-noise-ratio (SNR) -matching algorithm -Pareto optimality theory - Deep learning - peak signal-to-noise ratio - Adam optimization algorithm - Euclidean distance	LTE	-Video file - images	D2D cluster	-Cellular -D2D

[30][31]	- Proposed D2D caching according to Smart-Devices (SDs) subscribers different.	-water-filling algorithm	5G	Cashed video	-D2D cluster -Resource allocation	-Cellular -D2D
[32][43] [41][54] [55]	-Proposed Smart-Device to Smart-Device communication without human interaction. -optimization data delivery framework During communication over fast-moving vehicles. - Proposed Enhancement of multimedia streaming services for rider traveling in vehicles.	-Network simulator programs -fault-tolerant algorithm -bio-inspired routing algorithm -Machine Learning algorithms	5G	-vehicle videos -pictures files -multimedia delivery	-D2D cluster -V2V cluster -Interference Management	-Cellular -D2D -Wi-Fi Direct -C2V
[33]	- Proposed scheme for multimedia streaming over 5G-D2D and an energy.	-A greedy algorithm -Fast Forwarding Algorithm - brute force algorithm	5G	-Video streaming -Video caching	-D2D cluster -Resource allocation	-Cellular -D2D
[6][34]	Proposed resource-sharing scheme for multiple D2D groups and cellular.	-interference alignment algorithm -Shannon's equation	5G	Video sharing	-Interference management -Resource allocation -D2D cluster	-Cellular -D2D
[40][41]	-Proposed 5G-UHD Ultra-High-Definition framework achieving adaptive. -Proposed a cross-layer based framework for the transmission of High-Efficiency Video Coding.	-scheduling algorithm -full search algorithm -max-slope algorithm	5G	Video streaming	-Resource allocation	-Cellular -D2D
[42]	-Proposed architecture D2D communication based on the forthcoming D2D features of 5G networks. -analyzed network-assisted D2D clustering.	-Cluster formation algorithm -merge and split algorithm -game theory -beyond theory	5G LTE-A	Data	D2D cluster	-Cellular -D2D -Wi-Fi Direct
[43]	-Proposed routing method based 5G D2D to vehicular networks and V2V cluster.	-clustering algorithm	5G LTE	Multimedia	-Interference management -Resource allocation -D2D cluster	-Cellular -D2D -IEEE 802.11
[44]	-Proposed a simple and effective algorithm for cluster formation and distance-based resource allocation in Smart-Device to Smart-Device.	-cluster formation algorithm - Distance algorithm	5G LTE-A	Data	-Resource allocation	-Cellular -D2D
[49][50]	- Proposed cluster solution for multimedia delivery in an LTE D2D using Wi-Fi Direct to reduce energy.	-Test-bed measurements -discovery algorithm	LTE	-Multimedia stream -Video file -Video caching	-Resource allocation - D2D cluster	-Cellular -D2D -Wi-Fi Direct
[51][52] [53][65] [67][7]	-Proposed faster route of multimedia sharing among the users of the smart city. -Presented an e-Learning system based on IoT for the synchronous and asynchronous communications. -multi-focus images techniques	-An Efficient algorithm -complexity aware algorithms -fusion algorithm - WEKA - classifiers, clustering algorithms - feature selection algorithms -SVM -consolidation algorithm	5G 4G	-Multimedia streaming -images -video Cameras - video conferences	-Resource allocation -Energy efficiency	-IoT - IoMT

[60][61] [62][63] [64][66] [74][75]	-an improved adaptive Huffman coding algorithm -Enhancing video quality and Quality of Experience - proposed a QoE-aware video quality takes considering scalable video coding.	-Huffman coding Algorithm -compression algorithm -stochastic optimization -SNR -Advanced Video Coding -SVM - Benford's law -Emotion vector	Cloud 5G	-Video Coding -JPEG compression -video clips -video compression	-Data compression methods	-Wireless -cloud -V2X
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Table 3 will discuss some articles based on the requirements and objectives of the fifth generation 5G of communications.

TABLE 3: Results and Criticism.

Ref. no	Results/Conclusions	Criticism
[22][30][31]	The offloading was optimized by fetching pre-fetched video data in the local hotspot cache and the D2D communication.	These caching solutions are cause a delay in the case of live streaming but they efficient for the stored video.
[23][25][34]	- Classification of User Equipment for live streaming and on-demand for the D2D scenario based on flow strength, delay, and jitter. -Enhance video stream component based on random quality optimization approach.	applied the proposed approaches on the distance between the transmitting and receiving devices is 50m, but the fifth-generation communication does cover the distance between 100m to 1000m and the number of devices expected is much greater than the mentioned when simulated Thus, these experiences lack the hopes of the fifth generation of communications. -The authors consider the implementation of caching D2D systems.
[24][25] [26] [37][38][39] [30][31][33]	-Enhancement of the status of random demands has been discussed in advance through the application of the optimal min-max demand plan. -improving caching techniques.	-These caching and Segmented Video solutions are effective for the stored video but do not present solutions for the case of live streaming. -The authors did not provide solutions for popular videos based on the real caching system.
[27]	Improve the transmission times of the cellular downlink between the video layers in the cellular network.	The work did not take consider both size video and optimizing transmission durations.
[28][29]	The video is divided into multiple data packets and users who consent the same packet are classified into one cluster.	The scenario needs that be more realistic.
[34]	succeed to reduce the interference from the D2D pairs to the cellular users based on the distance requirement	-scenarios are users usually static, some users or all users sometimes might be moving at pedestrian speed. But, the characteristics of high traffic volume density such as subway and high-speed railways, the high mobility feature of wireless communications will be prominent in 5G. - The average distance between the sender and receiver of a D2D pair is 50 m
[32]	Improving D2D communication without human interaction in both 5G applications advanced within WFD.	-The work needs to analyze this type of ProSe communication with a greater number of Smart-Devices (SDs). -The Smart-Devices (SDs) were placed on a table at an average distance of 3 m, and movements were not taken into consideration. -black pictures and white pictures, and at low resolution.

6. Some research issues related to the future of 5G

There are some research issues related to the future of Smart-Device to Smart-Device D2D communications with 5G can be listed in a set of questions for example, can 5G design support billions of connected Smart-Devices (SDs) and users worldwide, and can support a variety of services and applications, will 5G ensures low latency to avoid the bottleneck of the radio interface in real-time, does the 5G offer network features that are different from those of the traditional IoT scene. In Smart-Device to Smart-Device D2D scenarios, how to detection Smart-Devices (SDs) in area and how to calculate the distance between each Smart-Device (SD) taking into consideration some scenarios, the users be static or users may move at pedestrian speed or high traffic volume density such as the vehicle, subway and high speed railways, how applications provide road safety systems and traffic updates for Smart-Vehicle to Smart-Vehicle V2V communications and what automated mechanism exploits social connections between Smart-Devices (SDs) to create D2D dynamic social networks and information gathered from social networks can help share content in general and Smart-Devices (SDs) of similar interest can collaborate with each other to share content and does the D2D capability allow for efficient spectrum utilization, enhance network life, and allow Smart-Devices (SDs) to operate independently in situations where immediate access to energy infrastructure is not possible as well as many problems such as interference management, resource allocation, and live multimedia streaming, now current solutions to the state of live streaming are not enough as they rely heavily on caching and Segmented Video. And many questions and ideas for discussion of the future of 5G.

7. Advantages and disadvantages of the different types of Smart-Device to Smart-Device Communications

A brief overview of the advantages and disadvantages of Inband D2D and Outband D2D communications. Overall, the advantages of D2D Communication led to link reliability between Smart-Device to Smart-Device D2D, higher data rate, instant communication, low End-to-End latency, easy sharing of files from Peer-to-Peer P2P, improved voice and video streaming services, online games, improve throughput, low power consumption, IoT Enhancement [4]. Inband D2D, increases underlay D2D the spectral efficiency of cellular spectrum leading to high spectral efficiency, QoS management is easy because the cellular spectrum It can be completely controlled by the base station BS [18], can use the Inband D2D on any device. Outband D2D, non-interference between D2D and cellular subscribers, nothing is necessary to dedicate cellular resources to spectrum D2D [20]. The main disadvantage of Inband lies in the interference caused by Smart-Device to Smart-Device D2D users to cellular users. In underlay Inband D2D communications, D2D users use a common cellular frequency, which increases the probability of interference; D2D users, therefore, need efficient power control mechanisms. When a group of Smart-Devices (SDs) selects the cluster head and processes the requests of the bundled Smart-Devices (SDs) therefore needs to improve Spectral efficiency. In the overlay mode, Smart-Device to Smart-Device

D2D users use dedicated cellular frequency and therefore require a solution to reduce interference by allocating dedicated resources for Smart-Device to Smart-Device D2D communication. In D2D Outband communication exploits unlicensed spectrum, the use of unlicensed spectrum requires additional interfaces such as Wi-Fi direct, Zigbee, and Bluetooth because these technologies are usually different from cellular technologies available such as 3G and 4G [4][18].

Conclusion

In this article, we have provided a wide survey of the literature available on Smart-Device to Smart-Device D2D communication within the cellular network and Wi-Fi Direct WFD and provided solutions for video streaming, Cached, and segmented Video Download, and make a comparison between the articles with the mentioned techniques used in each work and Analytical tools then presented critical analytical based on 5G requirements. The survey found that the number of articles that were related to Smart-Device to Smart-Device D2D with Wi-Fi Direct WFD is few compared to cellular networks, it is considered an open issue.

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